

The order of formation constants was obtained by observing the shift of $E_{1/2}$ in function of the concentration of the ligand. The following equation may be applied⁵

$$(E_{1/2})_c - (E_{1/2})_s = \frac{0.059}{n} \log Kc - p \frac{0.059}{n} \log C_x$$

where $(E_{1/2})_c$ and $(E_{1/2})_s$ are the half wave potentials of the complex ion and the simple metal ions respectively, and C_x is the concentration of the ligand. The dissociation constants (Kc) of the complex ions calculated from the above equation for cobalt(II) and nickel(II) are 9.15×10^{-13} and 5.83×10^{-9} respectively. These values of dissociation constants indicate that Co^{2+} forms more stable complexes with EDPO than Ni^{2+} which is not in agreement with Irving-Williams order⁶. This may be attributed to the additional stabilization due to Jahn Teller effect present in cobalt(II). Thus polarographic study of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) complexes with EDPO, reveals the formation of 1:3 and 1:2 complexes respectively.

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Phenyl Acetate Complexes of Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), and Zn(II) with Nitrogen Donor Ligands

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THOUGH a lot of work has been done on halogeno substituted acetates¹⁻⁵ of first transition series metal ions, little has been done by varying the R-group of the carboxylates. Only recently Thornton⁶ and coworkers have reported some Ni(II) complexes of benzoates and substituted benzoates with heterocyclic amines. We have been studying the complexation of some divalent metal ion carboxylates⁷ with nitrogen ligand and reported earlier complexes of trichloroacetates⁸. This communication reports the studies on Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) phenyl acetates with some nitrogen ligands like quinoline, isoquinoline and 3-methyl pyridine.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Phenyl acetates of different metals were dissolved in absolute ethanol, treated with the nitrogen ligands in (1:2) proportion and the solution refluxed for thirty minutes over water bath. On cooling overnight compounds separated out. These were filtered under suction, washed with ethanol, followed by ether and dried in vacuum.

Physical measurements were made as described in an earlier communication⁹. Analytical data are recorded in Table-1 and spectral data in Table-2.

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS, CONDUCTANCE AND MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compound	Colour and form	Conductance (mhos. cm ²)	μ_{eff} (B.M)	% Metal		% Nitrogen	
				Found.	Reqd.	Found.	R.qd.
NiL ₂ Q ₂	Green crystalline	8.5	2.9	9.95	10.07	4.45	4.77
NiL ₂ (I.Q) ₂	-do-	9.2	2.98	9.83	10.07	4.52	4.77
NiL ₂ (β -pic) ₂	-do-	8.1	3.15	11.14	11.40	5.28	5.44
CoL ₂ Q ₂	Pink crystalline	9.5	4.84	9.86	10.03	4.53	4.77
CoL ₂ (I.Q) ₂	-do-	8.8	4.96	9.91	10.03	4.55	4.77
CoL ₂ (β -pic) ₂	-do-	10.2	5.1	11.22	11.45	5.26	5.44
CuL ₂ Q ₂	Green crystalline	11.5	1.75	10.56	10.74	4.48	4.73
CuL ₂ (I.Q) ₂	-do-	11.8	1.83	11.62	10.74	4.54	4.73
CuL ₂ (β -pic) ₂	-do-	12.6	1.88	12.01	12.28	5.26	5.39
ZnL ₂ Q ₂	White crystalline	10.5	—	10.92	11.02	4.51	4.72
ZnL ₂ (I.Q) ₂	-do-	13.8	—	10.86	11.02	4.60	4.72
ZnL ₂ (β -pic) ₂	-do-	14.7	—	12.25	12.54	5.22	5.37

Q=quinoline; I.Q.=isoquinoline; β -pic=3-methyl pyridine

TABLE 2—INFRARED SPECTRA (cm⁻¹) AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRA (K.K.) (ε)

Compounds	$\nu_0(\text{C}=\text{O})$	$\nu_1(\text{C}=\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$	
NiL ₂ Q ₂	1630	1410	265	355	9.0 (6), 15.2 (13), 25.1 (2)
NiL ₂ (I.Q) ₂	1635	1415	250	350	9.2 (5.8), 15.5 (15), 25.5 (30)
NiL ₂ (β-pic) ₂	1635	1420	255	350	9.5 (6.5), 15.3 (13), 25.0 (28)
CoL ₂ Q ₂	1650	1430	235	325	8.0 (9.5), 16.5 (33)
CoL ₂ (I.Q) ₂	1645	1420	225	320	8.7 (11), 19.7 (36)
CoL ₂ (β-pic) ₂	1640	1425	220	340	8.2 (8), 19.0 (30)
CuL ₂ Q ₂	1633	1410	250	350	15.5 (45)
CuL ₂ (I.Q) ₂	1625	1405	255	340	15.2 (48)
CuL ₂ (β-pic) ₂	1630	1420	250	345	15.0 (44)
ZnL ₂ Q ₂	1625	1410	230	320	
ZnL ₂ (I.Q) ₂	1620	1410	225	325	
ZnL ₂ (β-pic) ₂	1625	1415	230	320	

Results and Discussion

All the complexes reported in the present investigation are crystalline or micro-crystalline and have the composition ML₂B₂. These have fairly low melting points. All are soluble in common organic solvents, acetone solution of the complexes behave as non-electrolytes as the Δ_M values are low being in the range of 8-15 mhos. cm². Magnetic moment values of Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II) complexes at room temperature (25°) are indicative of high spin octahedral configuration, the μ_{eff} being in the range of 4.8-5.2 and 2.9-3.2 B.M. respectively. Copper(II) complexes have magnetic moment values in the range of 1.75 to 1.88 B.M.

In sodium phenyl acetate asymmetric and symmetric C=O stretching frequencies appear at 1610 and 1400 cm⁻¹ respectively⁹. These bands go to slightly lower frequency regions in the phenyl acetates of transition metal ions and shift to higher frequency regions in the complexes with nitrogen ligands. Further, most of the absorption bands due to free nitrogen ligands are shifted in most of the complexes to lower frequency region indicating their coordination to the metal ions. This has been further substantiated by the observation¹⁰ of $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ at 350 and 250 cm⁻¹ respectively in the far infrared region. The difference between the asymmetric and symmetric stretching C-O modes is of the order of 210-220 cm⁻¹ indicating bidentate nature of the acetato groups as this difference will be of higher order for monodentate acetato groups.

In the electronic spectra of Nickel(II) complexes in (chloroform base) solution three absorption bands appear in the 9.0, 15.0 and 25.0 K.K. regions assignable¹¹ to $3A_{2g} \rightarrow 2T_{2g}$, $3A_{2g} \rightarrow 3T_{1g}(\text{F})$ and $3A_{2g} \rightarrow 3T_{1g}(\text{P})$ transitions indicating an octahedral configuration. Extinction coefficient values also support the configuration. Comparison of the bands of a similar compound

with the diffuse reflectance spectra reported by Thornton et al⁶ indicates a little dissociation of the ligands inspite of the added base as the bands in solution spectra are at lower energy. It is quite probable that there is a distortion of the octahedron in solution as the two nitrogen ligands are in the trans position.

Cobalt(II) complexes give rise to two absorption bands around 8.0 and 19.5 K.K. regions which can be assigned to $4T_{1g} \leftarrow 4T_{2g}$ and $4T_{1g} \rightarrow 4T_{1g}(\text{P})$ transitions. These absorption bands and extinction coefficient values also show an octahedral geometry for these complexes. Calculation of D_q and β values (not given here) and μ_{eff} values are in conformity with a high spin octahedral configuration for Co(II) and Ni(II) complexes.

Copper(II) complexes show one broad absorption band in the 15.5 K.K. region. Though three transitions¹² $2B_1 \rightarrow 2A_1$ (ν_1), $2B_1 \rightarrow 2A_2$ (ν_2), $2B_1 \rightarrow 2E$ (ν_3) should occur in Copper(II) complexes due to Jahn-Teller distortions, these three transitions are very close in energy and often appear in form of a broad band envelope¹³. A distorted octahedral structure is suggested for Copper(II) complexes.

Zinc complexes presumably have an octahedral environment around the metal ion involving bidentate acetato groups.

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Stepwise Stability Constants of Mn(II) and Co(II) Complexes with 2-Hydroxy-5-Chlorobenzophenoneanil

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THE proton ligand stability constant and the stepwise formation constants of the complexes have been determined by the Calvin Bjerrum pH titration technique as used by Irving and Rossotti¹.

The complexes of Cu(II), Ni(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II) with (HCBA) have been studied potentiometrically^{2,3}. The present investigation deals with the potentiometric studies of complexes of Mn(II) and Co(II) with 2-hydroxy-5-chlorobenzophenone and (HCBA).

Experimental

The same experimental procedure as described in our another communication² was followed.

The following solutions were titrated potentiometrically against standard carbonate free sodium hydroxide (0.5 M) keeping the total volume of 40 ml.

(I) 0.8 ml. (0.998 M) $HClO_4$ + 4.0 ml. (1 M) $NaClO_4$ + 11.2 ml. water + 24.0 ml. dioxane. (II) 0.8 ml. (0.998 M) $HClO_4$ + 4.0 ml. (1 M) $NaClO_4$ + 11.2 ml. water + 2.0 ml. (0.01 M) ligand + 22.0 ml. dioxane. (III) 0.8 ml. (0.998 M) $HClO_4$ + 4.0 ml. (1.0 M) $NaClO_4$ + 10.8 ml. water + 2.0 ml. (0.1 M) ligand + 0.4 ml. (0.1 M) metal + 22.0 ml. dioxane.

The average number of protons associated with HCBA ($\bar{n}_4$), average number of ligand attached per metal ion ($\bar{n}$) and free ligand exponent (pL) were calculated using the formulae of Irving and Rossotti¹.

Fig. 1 Formation curves of (A) $Mn(HCBA)_2$ and (B) $Co(HCBA)_2$ at 30°C.

From the values of $\bar{n}$ and pL formation curves were plotted (Fig. 1) and the formation constants were determined by the usual computational methods. The values of formation constants obtained from least square method are summarised below:

TABLE

Temp. $30 \pm 2^\circ$; $\mu = 0.1 M$ in 60% v/v dioxane-water media

Chelate	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log \beta$
HCBA	10.85	3.64	14.49
$Mn(HCBA)_2$	5.68	3.89	9.57
$Co(HCBA)_2$	6.48	4.27	10.75

Results and Discussion

In the ligand it is the chelated phenolic-OH group which takes part in the complex formation and the proton is replaced from it by metal ions during the formation of metal chelate. Since only one proton per ligand molecule is liberated during complexation, the number of dissociable protons attached per ligand molecule is equal to one.

In the initial stage of the titration the ligand curve got shifted to the left (or above) as compared to the free acid curve due to the basic property of the tertiary nitrogen ($-C=N$) which accepts a proton from the strongly acid medium. The protonated species formed